

Gender Roles in Indigenous Food Processing and Women's Participation in Global Food Markets in Southwest

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Abstract: This study looked at gender roles in indigenous food processing and investigated ways to give women more authority so they may effectively participate in international food markets. Data were gathered from 250 respondents (100 men and 150 women) who worked in traditional food processing in a few chosen areas in Oyo, Osun, and Ogun States, Nigeria, using a descriptive survey approach. The main tool was a structured questionnaire that was reliability-tested (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.84) and approved by expert review. Women were more active in food fermentation (82%), drying (76%), packaging (68%), and local marketing (74%), whereas men were more involved in mechanized processing (64%) and transportation (58%), according to descriptive and inferential analyses conducted using SPSS version 26. A significant correlation between gender and processing activity was found by the chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 22.41$, $p < 0.05$). Two major obstacles to women's empowerment were insufficient training (71%) and restricted access to financing (80%). According to the respondents, in order to improve women's inclusion in the global market, capacity-building (78%), financial availability (75%), and cooperative creation (64%) are essential. The study indicates that in order to increase women's roles in indigenous food value chains and global competitiveness, gender-responsive initiatives, access to finance, and digital empowerment are essential.

Keywords: Indigenous food processing, Gender roles, Women empowerment, Global food markets, Nigeria.

1. Introduction

Indigenous food processing maintains livelihoods and preserves traditional food systems by serving as a vital link between agricultural output and consumption. Women are the backbone of indigenous food processing in Africa, helping to ensure food safety, distribution and preservation (Akinola, Pereira, Mabhaudhi, De Bruin, & Rusch, 2020). Despite their major contributions, women are still excluded from new technology, financial opportunities and export prospects that could increase

their involvement in international food markets (Hernandez, Alarcon, Berrospi, Lopera, Quintero, Reyes, & Olivet, 2023). The societal construction of gender roles in food systems frequently places men in positions of control over assets and marketing, while women are positioned in low-income, labor-intensive value chain sectors (Pyburn, Slavchevska, & Kruijssen, 2023).

This division of labour affects women's empowerment and their ability to make vital contributions to the efficiency of international trade. Policy changes that address underlying socioeconomic differences, improve skills and promote targeted empowerment are necessary for introducing indigenous women processors into international food markets (Malhotra et al., 2024). Although, research on indigenous food processing and women's roles in agri-food value chains is expanding (O'Brien, Leavens, Ndiaye, & Traoré, 2022). A study by Omotoso, Letsoalo, Olagunju, Tshwene, and Omotayo (2023) highlighted that majority of earlier studies have primarily examined Sub-Saharan Africa or global contexts, paying little empirical attention to the unique institutional, socio cultural and market constraints that indigenous women processors in Southwest Nigeria face. Furthermore, there is a lack of research that combines gender role analysis with practical empowering strategies for women's involvement in global food markets. (Cederroth, Earp, Prada, Jarach, Lir, Norris, Pilote, Raparelli, Rochon, Sahraoui, Simmon, Vissandjee, Mour, Arbogast, Armengol, & Mason 2024). This study therefore, investigated gender roles in indigenous food processing and examined how women can be empowered for active participation in global food markets in Southwest Nigeria.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to:

1. Examine gender roles in indigenous food processing activities.
2. Identify barriers hindering women's empowerment in global food trade.
3. Recommend strategies to enhance women's participation in international markets.

2.0. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to examine gender roles in indigenous food processing and women's participation in global food markets in Southwest Nigeria.

2.2. Study Area and Population

The research was carried out in selected agrarian communities across Oyo, Osun, and Ogun States in Southwest Nigeria. The study population comprised male and female indigenous food processors in these states, which were selected due to their significant engagement in the processing of fermented foods, cassava, yam and maize-based products.

2.3. Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

A multistage sampling procedure was employed for respondent selection. In the first stage, Oyo, Osun and Ogun States were purposively selected. Subsequently, two Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from each state. In the third stage, indigenous food-processing communities within the selected LGAs were identified

and respondents were proportionately drawn from each community. The final sample consisted of two hundred and fifty (250) respondents, comprising 150 women and 100 men. The greater representation of women reflects the actual gender structure of the indigenous food-processing workforce in the study area, where women predominate. The sample size was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination model.

2.4. Data Collection Instrument

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Gender Roles and Empowerment in Indigenous Food Processing Questionnaire (GREIFPQ). The instrument captured information on respondents' socio-economic characteristics, gender-based roles in indigenous food processing, constraints to women's participation in global food markets, and strategies for enhancing women's inclusion in international food value chains.

2.5. Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was pilot-tested among 20 indigenous food processors drawn from a non-sampled community. Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, which produced a reliability coefficient of 0.84, indicating satisfactory reliability.

2.6. Data Collection Procedure and Ethical Considerations

Data collection spanned six weeks and standards were upheld throughout the study, including voluntary participation, informed consent and confidentiality of respondents' information.

2.7. Data Analysis

Collected data were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations were used to summarize the data, while the Chi-square test was applied to examine associations between gender and indigenous food processing activities in relation to participation in global food markets.

3.0. Results and Discussion of Findings

The tables presented below show the results on Gender Roles in Indigenous Food Processing:

Empowering Women for Participation in Global Food Markets

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Mean	SD
Gender	Female	150	60.0	—	—
	Male	100	40.0	—	—
Age (years)	20–29	48	19.2		
	30–39	87	34.8		
	40–49	73	29.2		
	50 and above	42	16.8		
					Mean = 38.7 yrs
Marital Status	Single	58	23.2	—	—
	Married	164	65.6	—	—
	Widowed/Divorced	28	11.2	—	—
Educational Level	No formal education	35	14.0	—	—
	Primary education	64	25.6	—	—
	Secondary education	98	39.2	—	—
	Tertiary education	53	21.2	—	—
Years of Experience in Food Processing	1–5 years	59	23.6		
	6–10 years	91	36.4		
	11–15 years	62	24.8		
	Above 15 years	38	15.2		
				Mean = 9.7 yrs	SD = 4.6
Type of Indigenous Food Processed	Cassava-based (e.g., gari, fufu)	101	40.4	—	—
	Cereal-based (e.g., ogi, kunu)	64	25.6	—	—
	Legume-based (e.g., moi-moi, akara)	46	18.4	—	—
	Oilseed/Fruit-based (e.g., palm oil, locust bean)	39	15.6	—	—

Note. SD = Standard Deviation. Percentages are based on total sample (N = 250).

Table 1 indicates that women dominated in indigenous food preparation, with 60% of respondents being female. The average age of 38.7 years indicates that majority of the participants were able to continue processing activities and were in their productive years. Given that indigenous processing is primarily done in households, the majority of responders (65.6%) were married. A

moderate level of literacy, as indicated by the majority (39.2%) have at least secondary education, may make training and the adoption of new technology easier. Furthermore, respondents demonstrated a high level of involvement and expertise in traditional processing activities, with an average of 9.7 years of processing experience. Processing based on cassava was most prevalent, making up 40.4% of the participants' main product category.

Table 2: Gender Roles in Indigenous Food Processing

Processing Activity	Women (n = 150)	% of Women	Men (n = 100)	% of Men	Mean SD
Food fermentation	123	82.0	27	27.0	1.55± 0.50
Drying and preservation	114	76.0	36	36.0	1.56± 0.49
Packaging and labeling	102	68.0	28	28.0	1.48± 0.50
Local marketing	111	74.0	29	29.0	1.52± 0.49
Transportation and logistics	63	42.0	58	58.0	1.42± 0.50
Mechanized/large-scale processing	54	36.0	64	64.0	1.36± 0.48

Note. $\chi^2 = 22.41, p < 0.05$ (significant). Higher mean scores indicate greater women's participation in specific activities.

Table 2 showed that 82% of food fermentation, 76% of drying, 68% of packaging, and 74% of local marketing were done by women. Men, on the other hand, worked more in large-scale automated processing (64%) and transportation (58%). The results of the chi-square analysis showed that the kind of processing activity and gender were statistically significantly correlated ($\chi^2 = 22.41, p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Barriers to Women's Empowerment in Indigenous Food Processing

Identified Barrier	Percentage (%)	Mean	SD
Lack of access to finance	80.0	3.82 ±	0.41
Limited training opportunities	71.2	3.66 ±	0.49
Inadequate processing technologies	66.0	3.58 ±	0.51
Weak institutional and policy support	59.2	3.41 ±	0.52
Poor market information and export linkages	55.2	3.37 ±	0.54

Note. Responses measured on a 4-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 4 = Strongly Agree).

Higher mean values indicate stronger perceived barriers.

Table 3 highlights the main barriers to women’s empowerment in indigenous food processing. The most prominent constraint was lack of access to finance (80%; M = 3.82), followed by limited training opportunities (71.2%; M = 3.66) and inadequate processing technologies (66%; M = 3.58). Institutional support (59.2%; M = 3.41) and limited market information and export linkages (55.2%; M = 3.37) were also identified, albeit to a lesser extent. The elevated mean scores reflect that respondents perceive these barriers as significant, while the relatively low standard deviations indicate agreement across participants. The results suggest that financial, technical, institutional, and informational constraints restrict women’s participation in global food markets, underscoring the importance of interventions aimed at improving access to finance, capacity building, and market linkages (Saluja, Singh, & Kumar 2023).

Table 4: Strategies for Inclusion in Global Food Markets

Suggested Strategy	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean	SD
Capacity-building and skill development	195	78.0	3.79±	0.42
Access to credit and financing schemes	188	75.2	3.74±	0.45
Improved access to export and market info	173	69.2	3.68±	0.47
Formation of women cooperatives and networks	160	64.0	3.54±	0.49
Use of digital platforms for marketing	142	56.8	3.39±	0.52

Note. Responses measured on a 4-point Likert scale (1 = Not Important to 4 = Very Important).

Higher means indicate greater perceived importance of the strategy. The findings in Table 4 show that access to financial facilities (75%) and capacity-building programs (78%) are the most popular methods for empowering women in international food markets. These are followed by cooperative formation (64%) and better export information (69%). These initiatives indicate important starting points for advancing gender inclusion in international food systems (Kuteesa, Akpuokwe, & Udeh, 2024)

3.1. Discussion of Findings

Although women occupy low-paying and less formalized positions within the value chain, they play a pivotal role in indigenous food processing in Southwest Nigeria. This pattern is largely shaped

by entrenched gender norms, which culturally designate food processing and household-related agricultural tasks to women, while men tend to dominate higher-value, capital-intensive segments of the agribusiness sector (Hernandez et al., 2023). Women's limited access to key productive resources such as land, credit and technology further confines them to labor-intensive roles, despite their substantial contributions to post-harvest processing and food preservation (Obayelu, Ogbe, & Edewor, 2019). These structural and sociocultural barriers produce a dual reality: women are essential for sustaining traditional food systems yet remain underrepresented in areas that generate higher income and access to international markets. Targeted empowerment initiatives including skills training, collaborative participation, and digital resource access can mitigate these constraints and improve women's competitiveness and inclusion in global food markets (Sarker, Roy, Yeasmin, & Asaduzzaman, 2024).

4.0. Conclusion

The study revealed that women play a crucial role in indigenous food processing in Southwest Nigeria, even though they are largely confined to low-paying, labour-intensive positions. Major constraints restricting their empowerment and engagement in global food markets include limited access to finance, insufficient training opportunities, inadequate processing technologies, weak institutional support and poor market information. These results underscore the importance of targeted strategies to enhance women's access to resources, capacity-building initiatives and market linkages, thereby promoting their participation and competitiveness in international food value chain.

Recommendations

1. Government interventions should focus on improving women's access to finance
2. Government and other stakeholders should expand training opportunities and modernizing processing technologies to boost productivity and product quality.

3. Government and NGOs should enhance institutional support and providing better market information and export linkages will further promote women's engagement in global food markets.
4. Policymakers should implement supportive regulations, provide extension services, and promote gender-inclusive programs in the food processing sector.
5. Government should establish market platforms, information systems, and export facilitation programs will connect women processors to broader domestic and international markets.

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